

Expertise before augmentation: a practical guide to using generative AI during research training

Arjun Krishnan, Biomedical Informatics, University of Colorado Anschutz

Contact: arjun.krishnan@cuanschutz.edu | [@compbiologist](https://twitter.com/compbiologist)

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HOW TO READ THIS GUIDE

Start here (should read):

1. [Philosophy](#): Understand the “why” behind these guidelines
2. [Accountability](#): Learn the verification challenge
3. [Protecting development](#): Recognize AI’s risks to learning
4. [Communication](#): Know your documentation duties

Then, consult as needed:

- [Writing code or analyzing data](#)
- [Writing manuscripts/proposals](#)
- [Reading papers, making figures/slides](#)

Notes

- Throughout: Refer to **Box 1** for privacy and policy requirements.
- There are answers to **Frequently asked questions**.
- The “**How to Adapt**” section contains guidance on institutional customization.

0. Learning and AI; the Philosophy

Generative AI tools like ChatGPT, Claude, and Copilot can be transformative to your role as a scientific researcher. Learning how to effectively incorporate these tools will be important for all of our current and future productivity. However, as a researcher still developing foundational expertise, it is worth stepping back to consider how AI use fits into the purpose of your training.

The primary purpose of your time in the lab is not to maximize productivity or complete tasks as efficiently as possible. It is to develop into an independent scientist with distinctive capabilities, perspectives, and identity. This means learning to:

- Think critically and originally about complex problems
- Cultivate creativity and imagination
- Build deep expertise in a way that makes you better in that area than most people
- Develop your unique scientific voice and perspective
- Form professional relationships and collaborative skills

AI tools can be powerful assistants in your pursuit of these essential capabilities, but they can also become cognitive crutches that prevent the development of these capabilities. Using AI to bypass intellectual struggle may complete a task faster, but it robs you of the opportunity to develop the very skills that will define your career. These tools can amplify your capabilities, but they can also amplify your mistakes, give you a false sense of security, and conceal gaps in understanding behind confident-sounding, polished outputs, often accompanied by explanations that sound authoritative whether or not they are correct. And, when everyone has access to the same AI tools, what will distinguish you as a scientist is the depth of your thinking, the originality of your perspectives, and the robustness of your foundational skills—all developed through sustained, sometimes difficult, deliberate practice.

The core principle running through this guide is straightforward: build foundational expertise first, then use AI to augment that expertise. The threshold for “foundational expertise” is not a fixed number of practice attempts—research on deliberate practice makes clear that quality of engagement matters more than quantity. The threshold is functional: can you complete the task independently, explain your reasoning, and catch your own errors without AI assistance? Until that bar is reached, AI use in that domain risks bypassing the developmental process rather than supporting it. Once it is reached, AI use becomes not just permissible but genuinely productive.

These concerns go beyond the discussion about unethical/illegal uses of AI tools that could be very harmful to your, the lab’s, or the university’s integrity and reputation (**Box 1**). Therefore, the guidelines in this document are designed to go beyond widely discussed *responsible use* (which are, of course, incontrovertible), to help you use AI as a tool that enhances your learning and growth (*strategic, augmentative, instructive AI use*), not as a replacement for the intellectual work that develops you as a scientist (*pervasive, dependent, substitutive AI use*). Consequently, these guidelines are also here to help you, when you’re done here and enter the professional world, effectively wield AI tools to accelerate your work while having the ability to check, correct, and complement them.

BOX 1. You must strictly follow any rules surrounding AI use laid out by the journals (to which you submit publications), University policies, faculty policies for any classes you’re taking, funding agency guidelines, and organizations providing access to controlled-access datasets. As a researcher, it is your responsibility to be aware of these rules and carry out your work accordingly.

Along the same lines, in general, protect sensitive, proprietary, and unpublished information, data, and ideas. **First**, [change GenAI tool settings to keep your data private](#). **Second**, in general, never input sensitive, proprietary, confidential, or controlled-access information, data (any data covered by data use agreements), or ideas into public GenAI systems that will store inputs/conversations/outputs in remote company servers (and use them to train future models in case you are unable to control that at your end). This includes patient data, proprietary datasets, and confidential collaborator information. If you are approved to work with controlled-access datasets using AI, ensure your use of AI tools complies with the specific terms of your data access agreements. **Third**, you should refrain from and/or seriously consider inputting unpublished work (research plans, results), novel research ideas or hypotheses, preliminary findings, grant proposals in development, manuscript drafts, etc. The general idea is to avoid inputting details about ongoing projects, experimental designs, or research strategies that could compromise intellectual property or competitive advantage. If you want to use AI tools for or need assistance with sensitive information, talk to your mentor first and work with them to identify secure, local, or institutional AI solutions.

Scope and definitions

Generative AI (GenAI) tools refers to AI systems like ChatGPT, Claude, Copilot, and Midjourney that can generate text, code, images, or other content based on prompts. This does not include basic spell-checkers, grammar tools without generative features, or traditional citation managers.

Research- or research-adjacent tasks include any work that directly supports or relates to your research projects, such as literature review, experimental design, analysis planning, code writing, workflow creation, data exploration and analysis, results generation and summarization, presentation preparation, manuscript or proposal writing/editing, and project management.

1. You are accountable

If you choose to use content produced by GenAI tools to aid your academic or research progress, you are accountable for the results, and as the PI of your lab, your mentor is also accountable (see [Principle 3](#)). The **cornerstone of accountability is verification** and the resulting confidence in the final product.

Verification is not optional, and it requires expertise

Every output from GenAI tools must be rigorously verified, but verification itself requires expertise. You cannot verify code if you don't deeply understand programming. You cannot verify data analyses if you don't strongly understand statistics. You cannot verify scientific claims if you lack authoritative domain knowledge. Now, the problem is that:

- AI outputs look polished and professional
- AI explanations sound confident and authoritative
- Errors are often subtle and require expertise to spot
- The speed of AI makes thorough review feel inefficient
- The volume of AI-generated content makes comprehensive review exhausting

This creates a dangerous dynamic: the very efficiency that makes AI appealing also makes it easy to skip verification. But unverified AI outputs are potentially dangerous and they may contain errors you lack the expertise to catch.

Requirements for verification (more under specific sections below)

You must thoroughly understand and validate every AI output. *For code:* read every line, test stepwise, and verify correctness. *For writing:* fact-check all claims and citations. *For analysis:* verify statistical appropriateness and interpret critically. If you cannot perform this level of verification, you should not be using AI for that task. Using AI for tasks beyond your verification abilities is not a productivity gain; it's outsourcing quality control to a tool that cannot be trusted.

2. Protect your intellectual, social development

For certain research-related tasks, using AI tools to accomplish that task may be possible and more efficient than you completing it without assistance, but reliance on AI can result in the loss of a significant learning opportunity and overall deterioration of your conceptual, technical, and professional acumen. Here's why.

The illusion of competence

AI tools create a particularly dangerous illusion: they make you feel competent at tasks you haven't actually mastered. You can produce code that runs, analyses that look professional, and writing that sounds authoritative—all without developing the underlying skills. This feels like

progress, but this apparent progress stands on a weak foundation. The problem becomes apparent when:

- You need to modify AI-generated code and don't know how
- You're asked to explain your analysis and realize you don't understand what you did
- You face a novel problem AI can't solve and discover you lack fundamental skills
- You need to catch errors but don't have the expertise to recognize them
- You interview for jobs and can't demonstrate independent capabilities

During your training period, this is catastrophic. You might feel productive because AI helps you complete tasks quickly, but you're not developing the expertise that will define your career. By the time you realize you can't work independently, you've already lost critical years of skill development.

So, the general principle is this: for areas where you are still developing proficiency (e.g., writing code or manuscripts, developing rigorous scientific projects, etc.), unless you're using it in a *strictly* instructive way, using AI is almost always the wrong choice, even when it seems more efficient. The "inefficiency" of struggling through a task yourself is actually the mechanism by which you develop expertise, creativity, and independent thinking.

So... considering using AI for a task?

Ask yourself: Is this a skill I'm still developing? Will AI prevent me from struggling through difficulties that build understanding? Will it prevent me from seeking human feedback and collaboration? Am I avoiding discomfort rather than building on mastered skills?

Especially avoid AI for: tasks you have not yet independently mastered, learning new concepts, reading literature (particularly in your first 2–3 years), writing first drafts, core data analysis and interpretation, developing research questions, and situations where human discussion would provide more learning.

When you do use AI after sufficient independent practice:

- Use it only after you've made substantial progress yourself
- Default to using AI as a critique (e.g., spotting errors, issues with clarity/logic, etc.), not as a provider of solutions
- Always revise AI suggestions in your own voice and verify with your own understanding

Practically speaking, students in their first 1-3 years should prioritize skill-building without AI assistance in core competencies (coding, data analysis, writing), except when using it in a *strictly* instructive way. Early-stage or more senior members who have demonstrated mastery in these competencies may use AI more liberally in an augmentative way to boost productivity.

Using AI for practicing socio-intellectual skills you are developing

After you've completed substantive intellectual work independently, AI tools with voice mode can be valuable for practicing professional skills through simulation and iteration.

EXAMPLE USE CASES

Comprehensive exam practice: “You are a faculty member with expertise in [relevant fields]. Based on this research proposal, ask questions testing my understanding of rationale, methodology, limitations, alternatives, and foundational knowledge. Ask one question at a time via voice mode. After my answer, critique my clarity, logic, brevity, and correctness, then suggest improvements.”

Networking/collaboration conversation practice: “You are [Dr. X], a leader in [field] whose work I’d like to discuss at an upcoming conference. I want to practice a brief conversation where I: introduce my work, explain why I’m interested in their research, and explore potential collaboration. Respond as they might, ask questions about my work, and afterward give me feedback on how I could be more concise/compelling.”

Teaching/mentoring preparation: “I need to explain [concept/method] to [audience]. First, let me explain it to you as if you’re a student. Then critique my explanation: Was it clear? Did I use appropriate analogies? Did I assume too much prior knowledge? What questions might the student ask that I should be prepared for?”

Career development conversation preparation: “I’m preparing for a career discussion with my mentor about [postdoc positions/industry transition/academic career]. Help me prepare by: asking me to articulate my goals and rationale, questioning whether my plans align with my stated interests, identifying potential concerns my mentor might raise, and helping me practice addressing difficult questions about my progress or direction.”

These uses treat AI as a practice partner for skills requiring repetition and feedback, like a sparring partner in sports. You maintain ownership of ideas and intellectual work; AI provides iteration opportunities that would be impractical to get from busy mentors.

Requirements

- Complete the substantive work first (write the proposal, complete the experiment, create the figures, develop the ideas)
- Use AI for practicing articulation and refinement, not for generating content or ideas
- Critically evaluate AI’s feedback. It may miss domain-specific nuances. More generally, AI feedback is a starting point, not authoritative truth
- Make sure to practice with real humans (mentors, labmates) for final preparation

Give some thought to developing your scientific identity

Part of your training is figuring out what kind of scientist you are and want to become. This includes gaining clarity on: what questions excite you and why, what approaches feel natural vs. which require growth, how you think about problems differently than others, what unique perspectives you seem to be bringing to the table, what you value in scientific work, and how you communicate ideas in your distinctive way.

Over-reliance on AI, particularly for reading, writing, and thinking tasks, can prevent you from discovering and developing this identity. AI produces “average” outputs based on patterns in training data. Your goal is not to be average, but to develop a distinctive perspective and approach that makes you valuable as a collaborator and independent scientist.

3. Communicate and document your AI use

Inform your mentor

If you use GenAI tools for any part of your research (or research-adjacent tasks; see [Scope and definitions](#)) associated with your lab, inform your mentor within one week of use or one week before external submission, whichever is earlier. Whether you used it to accomplish major or minor tasks — writing/editing code, writing/editing proposals/manuscripts, summarizing literature, generating images, making slides/posters, etc. — discuss this with your mentor. If you do not inform your mentor about GenAI use and issues arise (incorrect statements, falsification, license infringement, plagiarism, policy violations, disqualification of application/proposal for being flagged as “AI-generated”, etc.), you will bear those consequences without the support that transparency would have provided.

Beyond this requirement, proactively seek conversations when you’re considering using AI for tasks you haven’t mastered, finding yourself reaching for AI tools more frequently, unsure whether you’ve developed sufficient proficiency, feeling AI might be hindering your learning, or wanting guidance on reducing AI dependence. These conversations ensure your time in the lab results in deep, distinctive expertise that will define your career.

Inform your collaborators

Be transparent about GenAI use with all collaborators working on projects with you, inside and outside the lab. They’re investing time and resources and have a right to know what tools you’re using. This transparency should happen before or during work, not as an afterthought.

Document everything

Always track (in your research notes, code documentation/comments, and project reports) when and how you used GenAI tools. At minimum, include:

1. Tool name and model version
2. Date of use
3. Prompt(s) used
4. Output generated
5. How you validated or modified the output: Errors or issues you found and corrected; How you verified correctness; What expertise you applied to evaluate quality

Minimal example: “ChatGPT 5 (2025-11-15): Asked about paired vs unpaired t-tests for before/after design. Confirmed advice with Zar textbook and Biostatistics Core. Verified assumptions met before proceeding.”

Save screenshots or text files of interactions when possible. This documentation is essential for reproducibility, accountability, transparency, and risk mitigation, and will help you effectively report AI use in research articles.

4. Use GenAI tools thoughtfully for computational data analysis

As a scientist, you need enough coding, statistics, and visualization skills that enable you to analyze your own data, evaluate statistical claims in papers, and collaborate effectively with computational colleagues. While you're not expected to become a method or tool developer, you need sufficient proficiency in these areas to verify that analysis inputs, procedures, and results are correct and appropriate for your experiment. This proficiency matters because AI can quickly generate code, analyses, and visualizations, but this speed and polished appearance masks serious risks.

The danger of computational black boxes

AI can generate analysis code quickly, but without understanding what the code does, you cannot verify the analysis is appropriate for your experimental design, catch errors in data processing or statistical testing, troubleshoot when something goes wrong, explain your methods to colleagues or reviewers, adapt the analysis when questions change, or recognize when AI has made errors.

The danger of confident incorrectness

GenAI tools produce code and analyses that look polished and professional, often accompanied by confident explanations. This makes it especially dangerous when outputs are wrong because:

- You can't spot errors you haven't learned to recognize. If you don't understand what correct code should look like, you won't notice when AI generates incorrect logic, uses wrong functions, or produces subtle bugs
- Running without errors \neq correct results. AI-generated code often runs successfully but produces wrong outputs due to logical errors, misunderstandings of data structure, or inappropriate methods
- Confident language masks mistakes. AI explanations sound authoritative even when describing incorrect approaches

Common AI coding errors you need the skills to catch

In coding

- Hallucinated functions that don't exist in the package you're using
- Incorrect syntax for package versions
- Logical errors that execute without error but produce wrong results (e.g., filtering data incorrectly, calculating statistics on wrong subsets, applying inappropriate normalizations)
- Misinterpreted data structures (wrong column names, data types, or file formats)

In data analysis

- Running inappropriate statistical tests for your data type, sample size, or research question
- Misinterpreting statistical results, p-values, or confidence intervals
- Reporting statistics it didn't actually calculate
- Applying inappropriate corrections for multiple testing (or failing to apply them when needed)
- Using wrong baseline or control groups for comparisons
- Seeing patterns in visualizations that aren't actually there
- Ignoring important experimental variables (batch effects, blocking factors, repeated measures)
- Ignoring technical limitations of measurement approaches (detection limits, saturation, background)
- Applying parametric tests when assumptions aren't met

The confirmation bias trap

This deserves special emphasis: AI tools tend to agree with your assumptions and reinforce answers you want to find. When you approach data with a hypothesis you want to confirm, AI may select supportive analyses, interpret ambiguous results favorably, overlook contradictory evidence, downplay alternatives, or generate conclusions that match your beliefs. This AI bias might lead to false discoveries, wasted effort pursuing incorrect ideas, and retractions.

Protection requires deep understanding of your experimental system, critical evaluation of analyses, willingness to question convenient results, and consulting colleagues who challenge interpretations, all of which are skills developed through independent practice and healthy skepticism.

The categories below reflect the mastery-based principle above. Many borderline cases exist, and discussing them with your mentor is always appropriate. The goal is not a rigid checklist but a coherent standard: use AI where you can fully verify what it produces, and avoid it where verification would require expertise you are still developing.

Acceptable uses (instructive/augmentative use after building foundational skills)

For writing analysis code

- Adapting standard analysis workflows you understand conceptually
- Generating plotting code for standard visualizations (bar plots, scatter plots, heatmaps)
- Learning new R/Python syntax for operations you conceptually understand
- Generating boilerplate code for data wrangling operations you have independently mastered
- Getting help with data import/export and file format conversions you understand

For troubleshooting

- Troubleshooting installation or configuration issues
- Debugging syntax errors after you've attempted to understand and fix them yourself
- Understanding error messages from R/Python after reading them carefully yourself
- Getting suggestions for why code isn't producing expected output (but verify suggestions)

For learning

- Understanding basic programming concepts (loops, conditionals, functions)
- Learning data structure basics (data frames, vectors, lists)
- Clarifying documentation you've already read but find confusing
- Understanding what parameters mean and how to choose them appropriately

For data organization

- Developing organization systems for project directories
- Creating documentation templates for datasets and repositories
- Creating templates for experimental metadata recording
- Designing data management workflows

Unacceptable uses (dependent/substitutive use during skill development)

Learning and skill development

- Using AI to write analysis code for statistical tests you don't understand (t-tests, ANOVA, regression, survival analysis, etc.)
- Having AI perform data wrangling operations you couldn't verify manually or conceptually
- Using AI to bypass learning fundamental programming concepts from tutorials/courses
- Relying on AI-generated code when you're still learning R/Python basics
- Having AI write code for tasks you have not yet independently mastered

Analysis and interpretation

- Uploading raw experimental data to public AI systems for analysis
- Using AI to interpret or draw conclusions from your experimental data
- Accepting AI-generated analyses without understanding each step
- Using AI to choose statistical tests without understanding which is appropriate
- Having AI perform power calculations or sample size determinations
- Using AI to normalize or transform data without understanding implications
- Having AI decide on outlier removal or data filtering strategies
- Asking AI to generate complete analysis workflows for your experiments
- Using AI to determine if results are "significant" or "interesting"
- Having AI generate visualizations or statistical comparisons from your data

Collaborative and social learning

- Using AI instead of asking your mentor, labmates, or core facility staff for help
- Skipping workshops, tutorials, or courses because AI can “handle the coding”
- Using AI to complete computational tasks that could be collaborative learning opportunities

EXAMPLE USE CASES

Scenario 1: You need to analyze flow cytometry data and compare two treatment groups. **Don't:** “Write R code to analyze this flow cytometry data and tell me if there’s a significant difference between groups.” **Do:** Learn what statistical test is appropriate for your experimental design, understand the assumptions, write or adapt code yourself, and only use AI for specific syntax questions.

Scenario 2: You're getting an error when trying to load your data file. **Don't:** Immediately paste code into AI asking “fix this error.” **Do:** Read the error message carefully, check your file path and format, search the error online, ask a labmate, and only use AI if you've exhausted other resources.

Scenario 3: You need to create a dose-response curve. **Don't:** “Generate complete code to fit a dose-response curve to this data.” **Do:** Understand the mathematical model being fit, learn what the parameters mean, use established tools, and only use AI for specific technical questions after understanding the approach.

Scenario 4: You want to quantify Western blot band intensities. **Don't:** Write code to quantify these Western blot images. **Do:** Use established tools, follow their tutorials, understand normalization approaches, and document your quantification method clearly.

Scenario 5: You need to determine sample size for an experiment. **Don't:** “How many replicates do I need for comparing three treatment groups?” **Do:** Consult with your mentor, statisticians, or experienced colleagues. Consider pilot data, effect sizes, practical constraints, and statistical power. Don't let AI make this decision.

When in doubt: If you couldn't perform the analysis conceptually (even if slowly or with a calculator/spreadsheet), or couldn't explain what each step does and why it's appropriate, you shouldn't be using AI to generate code for it.

5. Use GenAI tools thoughtfully while writing manuscripts and proposals

Writing manuscripts and proposals represents some of the core intellectual output of your research, where accuracy, originality, and proper attribution are paramount. While GenAI can assist with certain writing tasks, the scientific content, interpretations, and conclusions must always originate from and be validated by you, the researcher. Using AI to substitute for this work forfeits the primary mechanism through which scientific writing develops: the struggle to organize, express, and defend ideas in your own voice. Writing is thinking. When you write, what you're actually doing is organizing your thoughts, wrestling with ideas and how to express them with apt words in coherent sentences, and delivering cogent arguments supported with evidence. Using AI to generate early drafts therefore bypasses the intellectual exercise that writing is designed to provide.

Beyond the developmental cost, improper AI use in writing risks plagiarism, factual errors, and misrepresentation of your contributions, with consequences ranging from retraction to loss of professional credibility.

Common AI writing errors you need expertise to catch

- Hallucinated citations: AI may cite papers that don't exist, make errors in the reference (incorrect author name, date, etc), or misrepresent what papers actually say
- Confidently incorrect scientific claims: AI may state false information with authority
- Inappropriate statistical interpretations: AI may misinterpret your results or suggest incorrect conclusions because it lacks context and suffers from confirmation bias (seeing what it expects to see)
- Missing important caveats: AI may oversimplify or fail to acknowledge limitations that you, with domain knowledge, would recognize as essential

Without scientific and domain expertise, you cannot catch these errors. The writing will sound professional and authoritative but the content may be quite wrong.

Acceptable uses

You are *strongly recommended* to write the entire first draft of manuscripts and proposals all by yourselves, get feedback on changes/improvements from your mentor and anyone else who's involved/willing, and then revise the text all by yourself. The only acceptable uses of writing tools at these early stages is checking spelling and grammar.

When you're done with at least 2 complete rounds of revising based on feedback from your mentor/peers/collaborators, you can consider using AI to critique, explore alternative phrasing, suggest specific places to revise towards improving clarity and flow. Finally, you make/incorporate changes, read closely, verify accuracy, and assume complete accountability.

Why two complete rounds of human-only revision is strongly recommended

Scientific writing is not about transcribing pre-formed thoughts onto paper. It is the process by which you form your thoughts, discover what you actually believe, identify gaps in your logic, and develop your unique voice as a scientist. When you use AI to write or significantly revise early drafts, you:

- Miss the opportunity to discover what you think through the act of writing
- Adopt generic, standardized phrasing instead of developing your distinctive voice
- Fail to engage deeply with your own ideas and arguments
- Lose the metacognitive practice of recognizing what you do and don't understand

You will develop your writing ability only through hundreds of hours of difficult, often frustrating practice. There is no shortcut that preserves learning. The struggle is the point.

Unacceptable uses

Using GenAI to:

- Write summaries and findings from your data/results
- Write interpretations, discussions, or conclusions based on your data/results
- Add citations or generate references

- Write background explanations and scientific claims from other related work; you should have read and understood all cited papers and need to be absolutely sure that: i) the claim from previous work is absolutely correct, ii) the cited articles are correct, and iii) the biological interpretation is accurate in the context of your work
- Write or significantly revise abstracts, as these represent your ability to distill and communicate your own work

EXAMPLES

Acceptable:

- “I’m describing a Western blot protocol in my *Methods* section. Critique this paragraph for clarity and completeness to ensure reproducibility”
- “What are some specific places in this paragraph that I can revise to improve logical flow while maintaining technical accuracy?”

Not acceptable:

- “Write a results paragraph describing the uploaded flow cytometry data showing T cell populations across treatment groups”
- “What are papers that support the link between drug X and pathway B?”
- “Here is a bullet list of thoughts/perspectives about the results. Expand each bullet point into a Discussion section. Add citations along the way”
- “Write three paragraphs summarizing these 8 papers about CRISPR screening methods to establish the background for my paper”
- “Condense the following text down to ~500 words”
- “Use the introduction section of the manuscript to draft a 250-word abstract”

6. Use GenAI tools appropriately for other research activities

Our daily research activities involve diverse tasks where GenAI can provide valuable assistance, but each requires careful consideration of accuracy, privacy, and learning objectives. The key principle is that AI should enhance rather than replace critical thinking, domain expertise, and direct engagement with research materials. Misuse in these areas could compromise data integrity, lead to superficial understanding, or violate confidentiality.

6.1. Reading and interpreting literature

Acceptable uses

- Asking for help understanding complex methodological concepts from papers you’re reading
- Getting suggestions for related concepts and research areas (but verify independently)
- Summarizing notes you have taken along the margins of a paper while reading it

Requirements

- Always read papers carefully, take detailed notes, and annotate the paper yourself with questions, confusions, and initial interpretations *before* asking AI for assistance

- For literature reviews spanning multiple papers, first create your own synthesis across papers. Only use AI to check for gaps or alternative perspectives, not to generate the synthesis
- Verify any AI-provided interpretations by checking the original text
- Be cautious with AI-generated literature overviews or synthesis across multiple papers
- Never cite papers you haven't read yourself

EXAMPLES

Acceptable:

- “Can you help me understand the difference between these two immunofluorescence quantification methods described in this paper?”
- “Give me a list of concepts (biological, technical, and statistical) I need to understand to fully comprehend this paper on CRISPR-Cas9 mechanisms.”
- “Here’s my summary of the key findings of this paper. Critique it and let me know if I have missed or misrepresented anything.”

Not acceptable:

- [Without reading the papers yourselves...] “Summarize the key findings from these 10 papers on organoid culture methods and write a paragraph surveying their pros and cons.”

6.2. Figures and data visualization

Acceptable uses

- Generate code for standard plots (following [Principle 4](#)) or help understand how to create the specific plot types you’ve decided are appropriate (violin plots, survival curves, heatmaps)
- Help with design suggestions for schematic figures or conceptual diagrams

Prohibited uses

- Never use AI to create actual visualizations from data (e.g., “create a publication-quality figure from this microscopy data showing cell counts across conditions”) or modify an existing visualization (e.g., “erase the last lane”)
- Don’t upload your Western blot image and ask “quantify these bands and create a bar graph”

6.3. Slides and posters

Acceptable uses

- Help with layout suggestions and design elements (e.g., “Suggest a better layout for this Methods slide that has too much text”)
- Help refine text for clarity and concision (e.g., “Help me refine this slide title to be more concise: [your title]”)

- Help create template structures or suggest organization approaches (e.g., “What are effective ways to visually organize a slide showing a multi-step experimental workflow?”)
- Generate cartoony/icon-like images/drawings if they don’t represent actual data or findings

Requirements

- Never use AI to generate content (text or plots) about your specific research results

Frequently asked questions

“Won’t students fall behind if they don’t learn AI tools during training?”

Building foundational expertise first does not delay meaningful AI adoption—it makes it more effective. AI interfaces are designed for rapid uptake; a researcher with strong analytical foundations can achieve productive fluency within days. What cannot be compressed is the expertise that makes that fluency valuable. Students who build foundations first lose no competitive ground and gain the verification skills that distinguish effective AI use from dependent AI use.

“Isn’t the acceptable/unacceptable distinction too rigid? What about gray areas?”

Yes, and gray areas are expected. The lists in this guide are illustrations of the underlying principle (*i.e.*, use AI where you can fully verify what it produces) not an exhaustive rulebook. When you are unsure whether a particular use is appropriate, that uncertainty is informative: it likely means your verification ability is not yet secure enough for that task. Further, AI technologies are fast-evolving. So, it’s good to constantly discuss where the boundaries are. Discussing specific cases with your mentor(s) and fellow lab members is always the right move.

“What if my field or program expects AI use from day one?”

Field and program norms vary, and this guide is meant to be adapted, not adopted wholesale. The core principle (expertise before augmentation) applies wherever independent analytical judgment is the training goal. How it is implemented depends on discipline, program structure, and entering skill level. See the **“How to Adapt”** section for guidance on institutional customization.

“Does this apply only to PhD students?”

The framework applies broadly to any training context where developing independent expertise is the goal: undergraduate research experiences, professional master’s programs, postdoctoral training in new domains. The specific thresholds and timelines differ; the principle does not.

HOW TO ADAPT THIS GUIDE FOR YOUR INSTITUTION

This guide is designed to be adapted, not adopted wholesale. Different institutions, programs, and disciplines have different training goals, timelines, and cultures. Here's how to customize these guidelines:

1. Identify your context: Consider your program type (PhD, MS, undergraduate research), discipline norms, training stage, and cultural factors. These shape how you calibrate the framework.

2. Calibrate the mastery threshold: The guide uses demonstrated independent mastery as the threshold for AI use: the ability to complete tasks successfully, explain reasoning, and catch one's own errors without assistance.

How quickly trainees reach this threshold varies by context:

- Complex skills (e.g., sophisticated statistical modeling): Mastery requires more time and more varied problem exposure; be conservative about when the threshold has been reached
- Simple tasks (basic plotting): Mastery may come quickly; the threshold still applies, but the timeline is shorter

Key principle: The threshold is always functional: demonstrated capability, not a fixed number of attempts.

Research on deliberate practice emphasizes structured, feedback-driven engagement over sheer repetition.

3. Customize content: For each task category (data analysis, writing, etc.):

- Add discipline-specific tasks and examples
- Modify tooling references to match your infrastructure
- Include field-specific norms and practices

4. Choose your implementation level:

- Strict policy (lab-level): "Trainees must complete X before using AI for Y"; Requires accountability and monitoring; best when PI takes responsibility for all outputs)
- Strong guidance (program-level): "We strongly recommend trainees complete X before Y"; Provides framework while respecting autonomy; requires clear communication about consequences
- Educational resource (institution-wide): "This framework helps trainees make informed decisions"; Purely advisory; requires robust mentoring support

Recommendation: Use a hybrid approach: strict policies for ethics/integrity, strong guidance for skill development, educational resources otherwise.

5. Address common concerns:

- Competitiveness: Emphasize that building expertise first makes students MORE competitive by developing distinctive capabilities
- Diverse preparation: Stratify guidelines by entering skill level; provide accelerated paths for well-prepared students
- Industry partnerships: Distinguish training goals from professional practice; clarify when students transition to "professional" mode
- Interdisciplinary programs: Focus on general principles; let advisors calibrate specifics to their discipline

6. Plan implementation:

- Communication: Reach students (orientation, handbook), faculty (meetings, mentoring guides), and administrators (policy docs)
- Support: Provide mentor training, regular check-ins during IDPs, community forums for sharing experiences, update mechanisms as tools evolve
- Assessment: Define success metrics (student confidence, independent capability, outcomes) and gather feedback regularly

7. Document and share: When creating an institutional version: Keep core principles (verification paradox, expertise before augmentation, developmental sequencing), Note modifications clearly and date your version, Plan annual reviews, and Consider sharing adaptations with the community.

Example context-specific adjustments:

- 10-week summer program: Compress timeline (5-8 attempts), intensive mentoring, focus on core skills only
- Computational PhD program: Stratify by skill type, add domain-specific tasks, include advanced topics
- Wet-lab-focused program: Focus on data analysis and figures, adjust examples to experimental data, provide more computational scaffolding
- Lab-specific policy: State personal accountability, require documentation, establish clear procedures, hold regular reviews

The goal: Thoughtful, iterative improvement in AI integration; not perfect policy from day one.